

Enhancing Leadership and Job Performance in Higher Public Education in Tanzania

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Dr. Hellen Mushi ⁽²⁾M/s Joshua Mjema (MSc) ⁽³⁾M/s Annie Maeda (MSc) ⁽⁴⁾M/s Nice Kahembe (Bsc)
⁽⁵⁾M/s Aidan Msuha (MSc)
⁽¹⁾ ⁽²⁾ ⁽³⁾ ⁽⁴⁾ ⁽⁵⁾Mzumbe University Mbeya Tanzania-
Website: www@mzumbe.ac.tz

1.1 Background of the Research

In the present competitive situation, most organisations strive to be successful and sustainable. Certainly, one of the significant variables in formulating the failure or success of an organisation is leadership. The word 'Leadership' has attracted growing attention in the theoretical and practical sphere for the past decades. However, leadership in tertiary education has been given less significance and is not investigated widely (Malenda, 2020). The job of university leader is large, complex and often filled with ambiguity (Cardno, 2014). Therefore, leadership and its effectiveness have been the aims of substantial debate and research from which more questions have occurred (Kinyaduka, 2019; Mesterova, Prochazka, Vaculik, & Smutny, 2015). It is widely believed that leadership has a straight influence on how effectively an institution achieves its goals and realises expected results.

This is mainly true today in the fast-changing and complex background of the 21st century. After more than a decade of economic, social and political turmoil, demand for open, trustworthy and honest leaders has grown tremendously (Lozano, Lukman, Lozano, Huisinigh, & Lambrechts, 2011; Northouse, 2013; Owusu-Bempah, J., & R., & Fairweather, 2011), and this has extended into tertiary education. Universities and colleges are now being drawn into the rising dilemma of leaders (Rebois, 2011) (Fraser, 2014). Tertiary education is being handled with a rising sense of distrust of individuals in leadership positions. Problems linked to violence on campus, the growing cost to attend college and interpersonal misconduct is causing severe concerns about leadership in university and college campuses (Fraser, 2014). There has been an increasing interest in the jobs of leaders within tertiary education institutions in present years driven by the altering shape of tertiary education leadership in the face of universal challenges within the sector (Black, 2015).

The expectancy of superior job performance and efficiency has resulted in growing demands for tertiary education liability (Nayyar & Mahmood, 2014). Leader performance in universities has become the main issue, both at departmental and institutional levels (Mtebe & Raisamo, 2020). Leadership is also one of the key factors affecting university's performance (File & Shibeshi, 2011). While there are several studies associated with the issue of leadership in institutions of tertiary education, up till now researchers have not sufficiently studied specific predictors of leadership effectiveness in such institutions (Mgaiwa & Poncian, 2016). Furthermore, university leaders as a population have not been extensively researched, which shows a gap in the research literature (Thrash, 2012). Similarly, there is a huge body of research associated with leadership and job performance of middle managers in business, but studies of leadership behaviour and academic performance in HEIs are missing (Almayali & Ahmad, 2012). Little is known about thriving leadership in the thousands of academic departments that constitute universities (Goodall, McDowell, & Singell, 2014). Thus, there is a need to build a model of effective university leadership as a base for institutional performance (Hamidifar & Vinitwatanakhun, W. Roodposhti, 2013).

Scholars are also concerned in finding out the degree to which leadership capabilities of university leaders can be anticipated by a blend of constructs including their leadership styles, and competencies in addition to roles to be an important aspect in leadership efficacy (Portnoi, Bagley, Rust, & In, 2016). But, there is a paucity of research linked with leadership styles and professional and personal characteristics of university leaders as predictors of their leadership effectiveness.

1.2 Problem Statement

The transformation process that occurred in the higher education sector has also changed the role of university leaders. They must perform not only in their scholastic capability but also as managers. However, some researchers (Lozano et al., 2011; Nguni, 2020) argued that those educationists who have been placed in leadership positions perhaps do not have the needed managerial competence and that many of the institutions offer little or no formal training and coaching. Deficiency of managerial competencies, abilities, skills, experience, inadequately thought out business plans, as well as resource starvation and adverse economic conditions, have been found to be the chief contributors to the failure of organisations (Bucur, 2013; Liu, Geertshuis, & Grainger, 2020). Thus, a framework of management competencies for coaching reasons has become crucially significant for the university leaders for it is the most helpful indicator for forecasting their job performance (Bucur, 2013).

Past empirical research has supported that competencies are positively linked to job performance (Mgaiwa, 2018; Munguatosha, Muyinda, & Lubega, 2011). However, some researchers have suggested that the debate of competencies in the entrepreneurial research is still in its initial phases (Chai, 2014), very limited, scarce or somewhat underdeveloped in the field of higher education (Wahab, 2016), and therefore presents several opportunities for the scholars (Bhardwaj & Punia, 2013). Laguna, Wiechetek, & Talik, (2012) argued that competencies have been researched in isolation and with a small attempt to recognise their shared relationships. To this end, the connection between broader groups of competencies and their associations with job performance and organisational success is yet to be statistically tested (Mitchelmore & Rowley, 2010). Though rising competition compels organisations to engage competent individuals, the connection between organisational success due to job performance and managerial competencies still remains a significant issue in the organisational literature (Crook, Todd, Combs, Woehr, & Ketchen Jr, 2011).

The expansion and growth of many higher education institutions would not have easily achieved without countering numerous challenges like financing, quality and the improvement in technology. There are also new challenges in the sector as a result of internationalisation, globalisation, and liberalisation of universities. These have brought with them various requirements, approaches and dimensions to the university leaders (Akhtar & Kalsoom, 2012). Consequently, in order to meet all these challenges, a strong sense of self-efficacy is vital among the university leaders for them to thrive and sustain. According to Bandura, (2001), the significance of self- efficacy in leadership situation is when they are confronted with setbacks or obstacles, and only those with a strong faith in their abilities will strengthen their efforts to master the challenge. He also stressed that individuals with a high self- efficacy will likely take a wider view of a job in order to establish the finest plan. Hassan, Alasmari, & Ahmed, (2015) concurred that difficulties often motivate persons with high self-efficacy to superior efforts.

Many studies have revealed a positive relationship between leader's self-efficacy and job performance, and that leaders' self-efficacy looks to be a promising construct for understanding their behaviour and motivation. However, it has yet been comparatively studied especially in the education sector (Tschannen-Moran & Gareis, 2007). Furthermore leaders' self-efficacy research is still very much in its early years (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2008). In addition, the literature of self-efficacy in the university leader's job performance specifically in the tertiary education institutions of Tanzania is sparse and somewhat understudied (Nayyar & Mahmood, 2014).

The present higher learning system of Tanzania could be explained as 'non-market framed' and it was not geared towards market principles and requirements. According to Kessy, (2020), universities are required to become customer oriented, adopt the marketplace and work as a full business venture in order to move ahead in the international competitive environment. In view of the transformations that have happened in higher education, it would not be wrong to state that learning orientation is the need of today's higher education institutions, because learning orientation is the degree to which an organisation gets and shares information about market changes, customer requirements and competitor actions, as well as advancements in new technologies to produce new services or products that are better to those of competitors (Mashenene, 2019; Mtebe & Raisamo, 2020)

Research scholars still believe that the area of learning orientation with respect to job performance has been less studied (Long, 2013). Learning orientation still needs more research due to the very small number of studies (Darmanto, S., Harsono, & Haryono, 2014). Careful examination related to learning is sparse, particularly in the perspective of performance effects (Jantunen, Nummela, Puumalainen, & Saarenketo, 2008). Even though the importance of learning in the area of global business has been extensively accepted, researches concerning learning orientation across borders (Jantunen et al., 2008) and in the framework of the exporting realm (Souchon, Sy-Changco, & Dewsnap, 2012) are limited. Although the learning orientation has received considerable attention in the scholarly literature, however, the use of learning orientation as a variable especially with job performance is lacking. Thus, this study looks into the learning orientation variable as one of the factors affecting university leader' job performance specifically in Tanzania higher education institutions.

From the above discussion it is concurred that by focusing on their self-efficacy to make them confident in their abilities to take timely and productive actions, managerial competencies to make them managerially strong in addition to their scholastic capabilities, and learning orientation to understand and cadre the prevailing needs of markets, clients, and other stakeholders make a suitable mix of variables to increase the job performance of university leaders.

Extensive studies have been concentrated on the jobs of chancellors, presidents and deans, and leadership catastrophe in managing the higher learning institutions has been discovered (Coats, 2000). The search for solutions to this leadership issue directs many researchers to believe that the university leader development is the least researched and most misunderstood management procedure (Gmelch, 2013). Mohamad, Daud, & Harun (2014) emphasised that the university leadership should be flexible and should bring transformation in order to attain academic excellence because they are experiencing multifaceted challenges (Hamidifar, 2012). The enhanced difficulty of the leadership role in the tertiary education setting has gained attention as a topic of study over the past years (Wahab, 2016). According to Wahab (2016) argued that bosses at every level of the organisation need leadership that is to visualise, to inspire and to initiate change. However, what is needed more is entrepreneurial leadership because it is vital for the future of organisations. By embracing entrepreneurial leadership it is hypothesised that this variable contributes to job performance as what Mohtar & Rahim (2014) suggest it enhances the organisational performance.

According to Chai (2014), entrepreneurial leadership and how to be successful in implementing entrepreneurial activities are valuable subjects and revolutionary ideas for future research in higher education. Despite the essential effect of entrepreneurial leadership on developing organisational performance and leadership effectiveness, the significant role this leadership behaviour can play in enhancing educational organisations has not been fully studied (Lebusa, 2009). Moreover, literature on the effect of entrepreneurial leadership on performance improvement of educational institutions is sparse (Pihie, Asimiran, & Bagheri, 2014).

Furthermore, little is known about the entrepreneurial leadership construct. According to Pihie & Bagheri (2013) there is much needs to be done to explain the characteristics and role of tomorrow's leaders, new thinking patterns and new organisational designs, and that entrepreneurial leadership may offer one answer. Bakar & Mahmood (2014) emphasised that entrepreneurial leadership is becoming a worldwide need and that the more understanding will be formed around the elements including this concept, the more the concept itself can be understood. Other researchers have emphasised on leadership types but hardly had they fully discovered the functions and concepts of entrepreneurial leadership in the public sector. Even though there are some subjective facts of the functions of entrepreneurial leadership in the public sector, limited academic work has been carried out to examine the meaning of entrepreneurship in the public sector (Hunter, 2013; Park, 2012) or the vital functions of entrepreneurial leadership for nurturing positive behaviours in public sector settings. As studies on the indirect effect of entrepreneurial leadership on performance improvement in educational institutions is scarce (Park, 2012; Pihie & Bagheri, 2013), there is

a need to study the entrepreneurial leadership behaviour to enhance the leader's job performance of higher education institutions so that they respond all the challenges in the changing environment.

Higher education institutions have to be receptive to the transformations in both outside and inside environments in order to stay relevant, being willing and ready to adapt strategies where need most, and to cater appropriately diverse public (Ellis & Miller, 2014). Universities are strongly intertwined with the wider national environment. Therefore, it is likely to argue that the national environment of university leaders may shape their activities in entrepreneurial endeavours (De Silva, 2012).

Transformational model theoretically identifies the possible moderating effect of the situation on the effectiveness of leader behaviour (Pawar & Eastman, 1997), but few researches have in reality tested for such moderating influences (Bass, 1996; Podsakoff & Bommer, 1996), and as pointed out by Yukl (1999), there is not much statistical proof of important moderator variables. Previous research has also shown uncertainty about the environment and its impact on decision making and entrepreneurial strategy in many ways (West & Drnevich, 2010). The discussion has shown that all three predictors of performance and job performance of university leaders itself are affected by the environment. So there is a great need to observe the influence of dynamic environment on these variables relationship. By studying the moderating effect of a dynamic environment with the combination of these variables, and specifically, in the higher education institution context will increase an understanding to which extent dynamic environment exists and affect the job performance of university leaders. This leads to the following research questions;

1.3 Research Questions

Based on the research problem the following research questions have been formulated as a basis for this study.

1. Is there a significant relationship between managerial competency, self-efficacy, learning orientation and job performance of university leaders in Tanzania?
2. Does entrepreneurial leadership influence job performance of university leaders in Tanzania?
3. Does dynamic environment moderate the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and job performance of university leaders in Tanzania?

1.4 Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to gain a better understanding of the factors influencing job performance of university leaders in the higher education institutions in Tanzania. Specifically, the objectives of the study are:

1. To determine the significant relationship between managerial competency, self-efficacy, learning orientation and job performance of university leaders in Tanzania.
2. To examine the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on the job performance of university leaders in Tanzania.
3. To examine the moderating effect of dynamic environment on the relationship between entrepreneurial leadership and job performance of university leaders in Tanzania.

1.5 Significance of the Study

As the 21st-century starts, higher education is experiencing unmatched challenges, occurring from the convergent influences of globalisation, growing significance of knowledge as the main driver of development, and the communication and information revolution (World Bank, 2012). Universities itself, public and private and commissions that direct and govern higher education in diverse parts of the world are developing policies to respond to growing requirements for tertiary education. As liability stakes continue to be raised in tertiary education, it builds stresses on leadership which is more and more observed as a factor that affects educational conditions and consequently the quality of student education (Cardno, 2014). Tanzania is no exception to this trend. According to list of approved university Institutions, Colleges, Campuses, Centres and Institutes in Tanzania as of 4th February, 2019 (TCU, 2019) the numbers of private

and public sector universities in Tanzania were 40 and 18 respectively. This growth has aroused the need of a distinct and an inclusive leadership system to run universities that are growing at a fast pace.

As higher education institutions are multi-product organisations, an examination of how those institutions can get better efficiency is of greater interest not only for policymakers but also for tertiary education managers (Olivares & Wetzel, 2014) . One of the normally accepted tasks of changing higher learning institutes towards higher performance is effective leadership, as leaders are in the seats of power and they persuade and administer human, financial and other resources, in addition, to providing essential aid towards superior success and achievement (Bento, 2011; Osundina & Owoeye, 2020; Yukl, 2010). The literature in recognising certain variables that could be related to leadership efficacy of university leaders is very sparse (Al-Shuaiby, 2009) . Therefore, this proposal by focusing on the improvement of university leadership based on issues and problems related to it will addresses the variables that help university leaders' to improve their job performance. Research says it's the performance of leader who actually leads the performance of whole organisation towards success so the idea of conducting this research is to study the effect of entrepreneurial leadership and moderating impact of dynamic environment on the relationships between managerial competency, self-efficacy, learning orientation and the job performance of public sector university leaders of Dar es salaam, Tanzania. The researchers, scholars, practitioners, and organisations (leaders and managers) will be beneficiaries of this investigation.

Despite the extensive research work that has been carried out in the entrepreneurial and leadership literature in the light of the contingency theory and organizational change, in other words, the results call for further research to resolve this inconsistency. Moreover, in the view of lacking empirical studies investigating the university leader's job performance, and implications of the interaction between three determinants managerial competency, self-efficacy and learning orientation in the presence of entrepreneurial leadership and dynamic environment in the higher education institutions of Dar es salaam, Tanzania, this proposal will represent an attempt to fill this theoretical gap in the existing literature. In general, the research will have many added value and contributions to the boundary of knowledge as discussed below:

The proposal needs to reveal that there is a little empirical research work conducted to study the relationships between these three determinant factors and the job performance of leaders in the context of higher education industry of Dar es salaam, Tanzania. In addition to that, most of the work related to this has been far from empirical-based research work. Therefore, this research will add to the scarce empirical research stream by studying this relationship in the context of one of the developing countries like Tanzania.

Second, the said relationship of the three determinant factors managerial competency, self-efficacy, learning orientation and the university leaders' job performance, with the mediation effect of entrepreneurial leadership and in the moderation influence of dynamic environment in the higher learning institutions in Tanzania, is hence the first attempt to identify the mediation effect in the integration of three determinant factors and the university leaders' job performance.

The managerial significance of this proposal will be of a great value for practitioners since it has many implications as follows: First, if there is a significant role of these three determinants, i.e., managerial competencies, self-efficacy and learning orientation for the effective and efficient performance of university leaders which ultimately impact their organisational performance. These are the leaders who establish the quality management practices within their faculties. This implies that all the highly performance-oriented activities conducted by the employees are due to their leaders. Second, the results of the study regarding the significant impact of entrepreneurial leadership on the university leaders' job performance implies that the leaders of schools/faculties in the higher education institutions of Dar es salaam, Tanzania should establish and develop an entrepreneurial cultural that encourage pro-active behaviour, innovation and risk tolerance as learning opportunities and growth drivers. Focusing the effect of mediation of entrepreneurial leadership on the relationship between three determinant factors, and the leader's job performance of the higher education institutions in Dar es salaam, Tanzania might provide some insights into how the integration of

entrepreneurialism in their leadership behaviour could help in building the competitive advantage to increase the overall performance.

This proposal, however, will be very informative and of a significant value to policy makers for many reasons. First, it may reveal the importance of quality initiatives towards the university leader's performance which will have the influence on the overall organisational performance of higher education institutions Dar es salaam, Tanzania in particular and thus to the overall economy in general. Towards that end, policymakers can help university leaders to achieve a high level of products and services quality and offer them the required training and consultation. Second, this proposal will show if there is significance of entrepreneurialism to the organisational performance. Therefore, policy makers can facilitate organisations to be entrepreneurial / more entrepreneurial by providing many incentives and opportunities and by encouraging the training and consultation. Many researchers such as Russell and Russell (1992) state that for entrepreneurialism to be enhanced, all the organisational members should be engaged and involved in knowledge activities. Moreover, there must be a guide for policymakers as how to use entrepreneurial leadership to create and enhance the competitive advantage of an organisation. Having emphasised that, the higher education sector is the heart of economy for countries and one of the effective drivers of the economic prosperity, therefore, the policymakers should give more attention to the higher education institutions when they plan for the long-term development process.

2.0 Proposed Methodologies

The assignment will employ quantitative method in data collection. This assignment will be randomly selection from the lists obtained from the respective universities' websites. This will assure ownership of findings and relatively will require lesser amount of efforts during implementation of proposed changes, and will contribute towards sustainability. The main thrust of the design will be a combination of descriptive and analytical approach, using data from both secondary and primary source. Based on the nature of this research, most of the data that will be generated will be quantitative. It is important to notice other data will be collected through questionnaire, and document desk review. So to accomplish the objectives of this proposal; a quantitative survey questionnaire research method will be used through a self-administered questionnaire to measure the variables under examination.

2.1 Sample Size and Sampling Design

The unit of analysis for this study is individual (university leaders) in 5 public sector Universities, Campuses, Centres and Institutes of Dar es Salaam Tanzania. The respondents' attitude towards his/her job performance will be measured as well as their perceptions towards the influence of their managerial competency, self- efficacy, learning orientation, entrepreneurial leadership and dynamic environment on their job performance.

Survey will be done to all target population which are deputy vice chancellors, deans, deputy deans, directors/chairmen and head of departments of faculty/schools of 5 public sector institutions of higher learning in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. The proportionate random sampling design will be used for its simplicity, less expensive, and easy to manage (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010) . About 10% of direct targeted key stakeholders from higher education will be drawn as a sample size for this review.

2.2 Data sources

Both primary and secondary data sources will be used to inform the study. Secondary data sources will include but not be limited to various relevant documents. Primary data will be collected through field study.

2.3 Data collection methods

The respondents from 5 public sector Universities, Campuses, Centres and Institutes of Dar-es-salaam Tanzania will be randomly selected from the lists obtained from the respective universities' websites. A total of 500 questionnaires will be distributed. The questionnaire package consisted of a one-page cover letter and the questionnaire itself. The cover letter will show the purpose of the research study, anonymity and confidentiality of the questionnaire's respondent, and consent by the Mzumbe University for the safety of human subjects to enhance response rate (O'Sullivan, Rassel, Maureen, & Taliaferro, 2016) .

2.3.1 Questionnaire surveys

Questionnaire surveys will involve key stakeholders from public higher education through the use of semi structured questionnaires. A representative sample will randomly be selected from the sample frame as per a list of Public higher education that the project has managed to reach.

2.3.2 Documentary Review

This will involve a desk review of all relevant documents, including the higher education activities, other relevant documents. Review the various on-going initiatives in the city, the initiatives around the university as well as to identify linkages and synergies with other regional private universities activities. Consolidate higher education activities with current higher education policy and all relevant background papers. Monitoring reports will also be used and it is expected that this data and information shall be obtained from the research to monitoring system which include; different records, routine monitoring reports (monthly, quarterly, mid-year and annual reports), higher education steering committee and partners meeting reports, workshop reports, training reports and any other special studies that the higher education partners may have conducted.

2.4 Data Quality Control

In any research there are always possible situations that might interfere with the result and affect the internal and external validity. For the consultant's team to be more objective, biasness has to be controlled. There are also possible participants roles that can affect the evaluation such as the "good participant role" (attempt to provide information and responses that might be helpful to the study), the "negativistic participant role" (try to provide information that might confound or undermine it), the "faithful participant role" (try to act without bias) and the "apprehensive participant role" (try to distort his or her responses in a way that portrays him or her in an overly positive or favourable light).

2.5 Data analysis

Upon completion of data collection, combinations of both inferential and descriptive statistics will be used as techniques of data analysis. The quantitative data collected from the questionnaire surveys will also be entered into a database and subjected to statistical analysis with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science). This software will be helpful in generating simple descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages and cross-tabulations. The PLS-SEM approach will be employed in the analysis of the collected data for this research. Particularly, two major PLS-SEM software applications including PLS-Graph (Chin, 2010) and Smart PLS (Ringle, Wende, & Will, 2005) will be employed in the analysis and presentation of outcomes.

REFERENCE

- i. Akhtar, M. M. S., & Kalsoom, T. (2012). *Issues of Universities' Governance in Pakistan*. *Journal of Elementary Education*, 22(2), 81–94.
- ii. Al-Shuaiby, A. (2009). *Factors contributing to leadership effectiveness among Deans of Graduate Schools of Education*. An Unpublished Doctor of Education Dissertation. The George Washington University.
- iii. Almayali, H. H., & Ahmad, Z. A. B. (2012). *Leadership behaviours and academic performance in Iraqi public universities: A Review*. *Information Management & Business Review*, 4(12), 596–600.
- iv. Bakar, M. S., & Mahmood, R. (2014). *Linking Transformational Leadership and Corporate Entrepreneurship to Performance in the Public Higher Education Institutions in Malaysia*. *Advances in Management and Applied Economics*, 4(3), 109-122.
- v. Bandura, A. (2001). *Social cognitive theory: an agentic perspective*. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1), 1-26.
- vi. Bass, B. M. (1996). *A New Paradigm of Leadership: An Inquiry into Transformational Leadership*. Alexandria, VA: US Army. Research Institute for the Behavioral and Social Sciences.
- vii. Bento, F. (2011). *A discussion about power relations and the concept of distributed leadership in higher education institutions*. *Open Education Journal*, (4), 17–23.

- viii. Bhardwaj, A., & Punia, B. K. (2013). *Managerial competencies and their influence on managerial performance: A literature review*. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Managerial and Social Sciences*, 2(5), 70-84.
- ix. Black, S. A. (2015). *Qualities of Effective Leadership in Higher Education*. *Open Journal of Leadership*, 4(2), 54-66.
- x. Bucur, I. (2013). *Managerial core competencies as predictors of managerial performance, on different levels of management*. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 78, 365-369.
- xi. Cardno, C. (2014). *The functions, attributes and challenges of academic leadership in New Zealand polytechnics*. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 28(4), 352–364.
- xii. Chai, Y. K. I. M. (2014). *The Relationship Between Strategi Entrepreneurship and Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Malaysia*. *Disertation*, (August), 281.
- xiii. Chin, W. (2010). *How to write up and report pls analyses*. in v. esposito vinzi, w. w. chin, j. henseler & h. wang (eds.), *handbook of partial least squares : springer berlin heidelberg*.
- xiv. Coats, L. T. (2000). *Interpersonal behavior and the community college department chairperson*. *Community College. Journal of Research and Practice*, 24, 773-783.
- xv. Crook, T. R., Todd, S. Y., Combs, J. G., Woehr, D. J., & Ketchen Jr, D. J. (2011). *Does human capital matter? A meta-analysis of the relationship between human capital and firm performance*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 96(3), 443-456.
- xvi. Darmanto, R. S., S., H., Harsono, M., & Haryono, T. (2014). *The Relationship between Strategy Orientation and Marketing Performance: The Role of Organizational Change Capability*. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 4(1), 221–229.
- xvii. De Silva, L. (2012). *Academic entrepreneurship in a resource constrained environment*. *Doctoral dissertation, University of Manchester*.
- xviii. Ellis, J., & Miller, P. (2014). *Providing Higher Education in Post-modern Times: what do university mission statements tell us about what they believe and do?*. *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 9(1), 83-91.
- xix. File, G., & Shibeshi, A. (2011). *Department Heads' Self-Perception of their Leadership Styles at Jimma University, Ethiopia*. *Ethiopian Journal of Education and Sciences*, 7(2), 97–114.
- xx. Fraser, S. (2014). *Authentic Leadership in Higher Education: Influencing the Development of Future Leaders*. *Education Doctoral*.
- xxi. Gmelch, W. H. (2013). *The Development of Campus Academic Leaders*. *International Journal of Leadership and Change*, 1(1), 26–35.
- xxii. Goodall, A. H., McDowell, J. M., & Singell, L. D. (2014). *Leadership and the Research Productivity of University Departments*. *IZA Working Paper No.7903*. Germany, Bonn: IZA Institute for the Study of Labor.
- xxiii. Hamidifar, F. (2012). *Effective leadership in Iranian higher education*. *SFIMAR Research Review*, 7(2), 13–19.
- xxiv. Hamidifar, F., & Vinitwatanakhun, W. Roodposhti, F. R. (2013). *Developing an effective academic leadership model at Islamic Azad University*. *International Journal of Management and Business Research*, 3(2), 161-174.
- xxv. Hassan, A. E. H., Alasmari, A., & Ahmed, E. Y. E. (2015). *Influences of self- efficacy as predictors of academic achievement: A case study of special education students-University of Jazan*. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(3), 275-284.
- xxvi. Hunter, L. (2013). *The mediating role of entrepreneurial leadership: an investigation of the competitiveness of SMEs in the UK South-West food and drink manufacturing*. *Doctoral Thesis*. University of Plymouth, Graduate School of Management.
- xxvii. Jantunen, A., Nummela, N., Puumalainen, K., & Saarenketo, S. (2008). *Strategic orientations of born globals - Do they really matter?* *Journal of World Business*, 43(2), 158–170.
- xxviii. Kessy, A. T. (2020). *Higher Education and Prospects of Graduates' Employability in Tanzania*. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(9), 177–187. <https://doi.org/10.7176/JEP/11-9-19>
- xxix. Kinyaduka, B. D. (2019). *Implemented Instructional Models in Tanzania : Experiences from Selected Higher Education Institutions*. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 4(1), 84–97. <https://doi.org/10.20448/804.4.1.84.97>

- xxx. Laguna, M., Wiechetek, M., & Talik, W. . (2012). *The competencies of managers and their business success*. *Central European Business Review*, 1(3), 7-13.
- xxxii. Lebusa, M. J. (2009). *Entrepreneurial strategy: A prospect for historically disadvantaged schools in South Africa*. *The International Journal of Learning*, 16(5), 577-588.
- xxxiii. Leithwood, K., & Jantzi, D. (2008). *Linking leadership to student learning: the contributions of leader efficacy*. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(4), 496-528.
- xxxiiii. Liu, Q., Geertshuis, S., & Grainger, R. (2020). *Understanding academics' adoption of learning technologies: A systematic review*. *Computers & Education*, 103857. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103857>
- xxxv. Long, H. C. (2013). *The relationship among learning orientation, market orientation, entrepreneurial orientation, and firm performance of Vietnam marketing communications firms*. *Philippine Management Review*, 20, 37–46.
- xxxvi. Lozano, R., Lukman, R., Lozano, F. J., Huisingh, D., & Lambrechts, W. (2011). *Declarations for sustainability in higher education: becoming better leaders, through addressing the university system*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2011.10.006>
- xxxvii. Malenda, S. (2020). *Education Leadership for Industrialization in Tanzania*. *European Journal of Education of Education Studies*, 7(3), 213–225. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3757342>
- xxxviii. Mashenene, R. G. (2019). *Effect of service quality on students' satisfaction in Tanzania higher education*. *Journal, Business Education*, II(Ii), 1–8.
- xxxix. Mesterova, J., Prochazka, J., Vaculik, M., & Smutny, P. (2015). *Relationship between Self-Efficacy, Transformational Leadership and Leader Effectiveness*. *Journal of Advanced Management Science*, 3(2), 109–122.
- xl. Mgaiwa, S. J. (2018). *The Paradox of Financing Public Higher Education in Tanzania and the Fate of Quality Education: The Experience of Selected Universities*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244018771729>
- xli. Mgaiwa, S. J., & Poncian, J. (2016). *Public – private partnership in higher education provision in Tanzania: implications for access to and quality of education*. *Journal of the Global South*, 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40728-016-0036-z>
- xlii. Mitchelmore, S., & Rowley, J. (2010). *Entrepreneurial competencies: a literature review and development agenda*. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 16(2), 92-111.
- xliii. Mohamad, M., Daud, S., & Harun, M. Z. M. (2014). *Top Leaders Attributes in Malaysian Higher Education Institutions: Effect on University Innovation*. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 2(3), 56-71.
- xliiii. Mohtar, S., & Rahim, H. L. (2014). *Social entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial leadership and organizational performance: a mediation conceptual framework*. *Aust. J. Basic & Appl. Sci.*, 8(23), 184-190.
- xliv. Mtebe, J. S., & Raisamo, R. (2020). *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning Investigating Perceived Barriers to the Use of Open Educational Resources in Higher Education in Tanzania Investigating Perceived Barriers to the Use of Open Educational Resources in Higher*. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning Investigating*.
- xlv. Munguatosha, G. M., Muyinda, P. B., & Lubega, J. T. (2011). *A social networked learning adoption model for higher education institutions in developing countries*. *Emerald Group Publishing Limited*, 19(4), 307–320. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10748121111179439>
- xlvi. Nayyar, J., & Mahmood, R. (2014). *The effect of corporate entrepreneurship determinants on performance of public higher education institutions in Pakistan*. *Business & Entrepreneurship Journal*, 3(1), 19-31.
- xlvii. Nguni, S. C. (2020). *Transformational Leadership in Tanzanian Education A*.
- xlviii. Northouse, P. G. (2013). *Leadership theory and practice (6th ed.)*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. Nunnally.
- xlix. O'Sullivan, E., Rassel, G., Maureen, B., & Taliaferro, J. (2016). *Research Methods for Public Administrators*.
- l. Olivares, M., & Wetzal, H. (2014). *Competing in the higher education market: Empirical evidence*

- for economies of scale and scope in German higher education institutions. *CESifo Economic Studies*, 60(4), 653-680.
- li. Osundina, K. S., & Owoeye, J. (2020). Role of Leadership in Enhancing Workers Productivity in an Organization in College of Health Technology, Offa, Kwara State. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research | Social and Management Sciences*, 6(2), 18–37.
- lii. Owusu-Bempah, J., A., & R., & Fairweather, J. (2011). Does follower subjectivity matter in defining authentic leadership? A call for qualitative research. 2(2), 1-25. *Asia Pacific Journal of Business and Management*, 2(2), 1–25.
- liii. Park, S. M. (2012). Toward the Trusted Public Organization Untangling the Leadership, Motivation, and Trust Relationship in US Federal Agencies. *JThe American Review of Public Administration*, 42(5), 562-590.
- liv. Pawar, B. S., & Eastman, K. K. (1997). The nature and implications of contextual influences on transformational leadership: a conceptual examination. *Academy of Management Review*, 22(1), 80-109.
- lv. Pihie, Z. A. L., Asimiran, S., & Bagheri, A. (2014). Entrepreneurial leadership practices and school innovativeness. *South African Journal of Education*, 34(1), 1–11.
- lvi. Pihie, Z. A. L., & Bagheri, A. (2013). The impact of principals' entrepreneurial leadership behaviour on school organizational innovativeness. *Life Science Journal*, 10(2), 1033–1041.
- lvii. Podsakoff, P. M., & Bommer, W. H. (1996). Transformational leader behaviors and substitutes for leadership as determinants of employee satisfaction, commitment, trust, and organizational citizenship behaviors. *Journal of Management*, 22(2), 259-298.
- lviii. Portnoi, L. M., Bagley, S. S., Rust, V. D., & In. (2016). Higher Education, Policy, and the Global Competition Phenomenon.
- lix. Rebois, R. R. (2011). *Review and Evaluation of the Performance of Tanzania 's Higher Education Institutions in Science , Technology and Innovation*.
- lx. Ringle, C., Wende, S., & Will, A. S. (2005). 2.0 (beta). University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany.
- lxi. Russell, R., & Russell, C. (1992). An examination of the effects of organizational norms, organizational structures, and organizational uncertainty on entrepreneurial strategy. *Journal of Management*, 18(4), 639–656.
- lxii. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2010). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*, 5th ed. West Sussex: John Wiley and Sons Ltd.
- lxiii. Souchon, A. L., Sy-Changco, J., & Dewsnap, B. (2012). Learning orientation in export functions: Impact on export growth. *International Marketing Review*, 29(2), 175-202.
- lxiv. TCU. (2019). Tanzania Commission for Universities List of Approved University Institutions in Tanzania.
- lxv. Thrash, A. (2012). Leadership in Higher Education. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(13), 1–12.
- lxvi. Tschannen-Moran, M., & Gareis, C. (2007). Cultivating principals' sense of efficacy: What supports matter?. *Journal of School Leadership*, 17(1), 89-114.
- lxvii. Wahab, A. (2016). Factors Determining Perceived Job Performance of University Leaders in Doctor of Philosophy. Phd Thesis.
- lxviii. West, J., & Drnevich, P. L. (2010). The Effects of Environmental Uncertainty on Young and Small Businesses. Paper presented in Conference on Small Business Entrepreneurship, and Economic Recovery. In *Personality and social psychology review*.
- lxix. World Bank. (2012). *Education in a changing world: Flexibility, skills, and employability* (Vol. 69104).
- lxx. Yukl, G. (1999). An evaluation of conceptual weaknesses in transformational and charismatic leadership theories. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 10(2), 285–305.
- lxxi. Yukl, G. (2010). *Leadership in Organizations* (7th ed.). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.